

The Impact of E-commerce on Consumer Buying Behavior in Pakistan

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Abstract

Consumer buying behavior ultimately refers to the behavior of a buyer who purchases things based on his likings while a buyer's choice depends on things such as decision making process, shopping habits and choice of purchasing. In E-Commerce, it is like a vital aspect to look upon. It is looked upon and it should be because it helps at a greater extent in planning, creating and implementing business strategies. This study majorly focuses on how online shopping has entered and started impacting the business world, and investigates the dependent and independent variables regarding the influence of online shopping. Furthermore, this study also aims to reflect upon the aspect of how a decision is taken and what impact it brings to the purchasing decision. To move this forth, the independent variables that were also the major factors of online shopping included product variety, sales promotion, online buying behaviour of customers and shopping orientation while E-Commerce being the dependent variable. Their relationship was examined in this research (i.e, how E-Commerce imposes an impact on Consumer buying behaviour and why). Furthermore, this research was done in order to study the consumer buying behaviour, that is apparently a hypothetical shift that works as per the experiences an individual has; either positive or negative.

Keywords: E-commerce, Online shopping, Shopping orientation, Consumer buying behaviour, Sales promotion.

Introduction

E-commerce in Pakistan has come out as the most convenient way to buy and shop whatever is needed and it has not only brought innovation but also convenience. Whereas online consumer buying behavior is a hypothetical shift that works according to the number of experiences an individual has; either positive or negative. In the start, the transition of traditional shopping to shopping online happened to create a sense of concern among the several customers regarding the violence of the security and confidentiality, unauthorized activities and the quality difference between the ordered product and the desired product, etc (Vasic, Kilibarda & Kaurin, 2019) but as compared to the past times, these concerns have now reduced as compared to the past times, as people recognized the benefits of online shopping with time (Vasic, Kilibarda & Kaurin, 2019). Online shopping has increased on a bigger level and more prominently in recent years because of the fact that it brings light to a more easy and effective approach for shopping as compared to shopping traditionally (Vasic, Kilibarda & Kaurin, 2019). There was a comparison that had been done between shopping traditionally and opting for online shopping. The comparison showed that online shopping is easier and feasible than traditional shopping. Therefore, this comparison concluded the fact that through the internet, more information can be collected by making the least effort, where convenience is made sure and also the time the consumer invests in doing that (Monuwe, 2004; Nazir, Tayyab, Rashid, Javed & Sajid, 2012).

The internet has invented a new pattern for the people to shop traditionally. Customers do not have to wait for the opening hours or specific locations anymore; they may purchase virtually whatever they want at any time, from any place of their interest. Though the Internet is comparatively a new medium introduced to communicate where the information is exchanged (Joines, Scherer & Scheufele, 2003; Nazir, Tayyab, Rashid, Javed & Sajid, 2012). As per the studies, there are some variables such as product variety, time, trustability, convenience and privacy assurance that determine the consumer buying behaviour (Bashir, Mehboob & Bhatti, 2015) and facilitate buyers in shopping online from the data provided on the Internet about products. Moreover, some studies have also shown that the class, income and education of the

consumers are potentially interlinked when it comes to their purchasing decisions (Elahi, 2016). It was also observed that consumers do not go back to particular online shops again and again because of the convenience they provide and their time and cost saving ability but because of the fact that they find excellent customer service there. It automatically provides them courage and confidence about the quality of products they are most likely to shop for. And this convenient shopping method is also becoming a common trend in Pakistan as well.

This increasing trend in Pakistan has compelled the researchers to conclude that Pakistani youth is comparably more interested in the online shopping trend as compared to older people. So, it is essential to explore and assess the link between customer satisfaction and determinants to increase the online commerce participation (Vasic, Kilibarda & Kaurin, 2019). In Pakistan, the acceptance of these trends is more challenging. Many people are reluctant in opting for online shopping as they incline to shop traditionally because of lack of trust, assurance and authenticity in terms of sharing confidential information, unreliable payment methods and poor customer service. They usually do not trust the quality of products on online platforms; consequently, they do not prefer to shop online and they are very much satisfied with their decision. On the contrary, teenagers and young adults are flexible about their shopping methods as they have gradually started to take part in online shopping because consumers receive greater information through online shopping and they further get opportunities to compare different products and their prices, with convenience and comfort (Vasic, Kilibarda & Kaurin, 2019).

Apart from this, different surveys have concluded that most of the people are already engaged in online shopping. They prefer to buy things online, but there are psychological factors that limit their approach as well as social factors, not leaving beside the emotional factors, and privacy factors which influence the attitudes of buyers in online purchases (Nazir, Tayyab, Rashid, Javed & Sajid, 2012). The factors behind the consumers' behaviour were analysed and assessed by (Smith & Rupp, 2003). These problems have been identified for making the marketing effort, invoking a socio-cultural influence, considering an emotional factor. Also the psychological and privacy factors to experience the pre purchase and post purchase decisions. The studies also further identified that the consumers are affected by a variety of psychological factors, such as perception, motivation, attitudes and emotions (Nazir, Tayyab, Rashid, Javed & Sajid, 2012). While it was observed that the protection of privacy and security were the major problems behind the consumer behaviour when they make a purchase online (Nazir, Tayyab, Rashid, Javed & Sajid, 2012).

Furthermore, the online shopping trend is increasing with time and rapidly changing; as a result, various customers have started opting for online shopping from all around the world. Today, businessmen are entering the world of E-commerce alongside searching for various convenient solutions for Pakistan's sinking business sectors. This validates the acquisition of a large number of E-commerce businesses that have progressed through this tool. Not leaving aside the fact that online businesses have turned out to be one of the most important marketing and sales tools. E-business allows you to buy anything that is available on the internet (Nazir, Tayyab, Rashid, Javed and Sajid, 2012).

Moving forward, the internet makes it a lot more convenient for the businesses to gain information about their products and services that are available for their potential customers (Vesterby & Chabert, 2001). It was further asserted that businesses that do not have any physical presence must introduce themselves in the market, both on online and offline platforms. It helps the consumers identify the business and remember their name (Vesterby & Chabert, 2001; Nazir, Tayyab, Rashid, Javed & Sajid, 2012). It helps the businesses build their identity in the industry because businesses usually gain opportunities in terms of increased sales and a direct relationship with its customers through E-commerce. Not to mention that online businesses helped a lot of businesses in globalisation all across the world where many companies sell their product in the world in this while (Nazir, Tayyab, Rashid, Javed & Sajid, 2012).

Hypothesis

H1: Product variety influences the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

H2: Sales promotion influences the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

H3: Online buying behavior influences the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

H4: Shopping orientation influences the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

H5: Respondent's reactions influence the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

H6: Good customer service influences the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

Research Questions

- RQ1:** How does the product variety influence consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce?
RQ2: How does the sales promotion influence consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce?
RQ3: How does the online buying behaviour influence consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce?
RQ4: How does the shopping orientation influence consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce?
RQ5: How does the respondent's reactions influence consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce?
RQ6: How does good customer service influence consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce?

Research Objectives

- RO1:** To determine the influence of product variety on the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.
RO2: To determine the influence of sales promotion on the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.
RO3: To determine the influence of online buying behaviour on the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.
RO4: To determine the influence of shopping orientation on the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.
RO5: To determine the influence of respondent's reactions on the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.
RO6: To determine the influence of good customer service on the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

Literature Review

Independent Variables

Independent Variable 1: Product Variety

Demand for variety may arise due to the diverse tastes of individual consumption even when each consumer chooses a different variant. The economics of product variety depends upon the analysis of the effect of keeping up with this equilibrium in various circumstances and contrasting the level of item assortment for various market structures with one another as product variety increases consumers' interest in order to find a good match with their preferences.

Independent Variable 2: Sales Promotion

A sales promotion is more like a marketing campaign in which businesses introduce a temporary offering or different offers to increase the customer interest or demand in their products or services. Though there are many reasons why businesses choose to go for sales promotion, the primary one is to boost sales. It is applied for a limited time period with the aim to increase consumer demand and stimulate sales.

Independent Variable 3: Online Buying Behaviour

Online buying behaviour is the process through which consumers search for, select, purchase the goods and services through Ecommerce. Online shopping has gained identification over the years real quick because consumers found it more feasible and easier. And in reality, this factor may influence customers' online buying behaviour.

Independent Variable 4: Shopping Orientation

Shopping orientation refers to a consumer's necessities and needs are interlinked with the selection of outlets (Moschis 1976; Sheth 1983) and this interlink varies from consumer to consumer (Luomala 2003).

Relationship between Independent Variables and Dependent Variable

Relationship between Independent Variable 1 and Dependent Variable: Product Variety and Ecommerce

The variety of products a brand offers is often regarded as their standard of quality and then it influences consumers for choosing the best amongst them it has been observed that the brands that offer a greater variety of options are more compatible and require expertise in order to be perceived as a brand name with greater category or core competency which in turn enhances their quality cue and consumer base (Berger, Draganska, Simonson, 2007). They consider this an opportunity that is better than offering limited options. It is for the obvious reason that the greater variety in options can provide you a wider range of choices (Lancaster, 1990; Berger, Draganska, Simonson, 2007). The increased product variety is interlinked with market conditions both on the supply side and the demand side (Israilevich, 2008).

Studies have shown sellers do not find interest in the markets with non-existent costs and restraints (Bakos, 2001). The increase in product variety may also offer the possibility of customization. It will allow every

customer to make their own decision and choose their desired products (Bakos, 2001). On the other hand, customization is based on a set of preferences that the consumer identifies while technology makes the identification and tracking of consumers a lot easier, both on an online store and different websites. Keeping a good look on the consumer profiles helps get the relevant demographic information and understand the known similar preferences of the consumers. These techniques can be used to discover the preferences of specific consumers (Bakos, 2001).

More to this, consumers can also observe the number of sold products on E-stores. Products having higher sales mean it has greater demand and more consumers have bought it already where the worth of the product grows with the number of sales. According to the theory, when the number of users increases on one side, the number of suppliers also increases on the other side (Wang, Ai, & Zhong, 2019). Though, the economists have proposed that broader product lines may create entry barriers (Schmalensee 1978) as the retailers or brands often charge higher costs for offering greater product variety (Draganska & Jain 2005; Lancaster 1979). But at the same time, people who were seen choosing their desired product from a larger product variety enjoyed the decision making process. With respect to price dispersion, oftentimes there are quite better price ranges on the Internet as compared to the local traditional stores (Bailey, 1998; Clemons, Hann & Hitt, 1999; Brynjolfsson & Smith, 2000; Israilevich, 2008).

H1: Product variety influences the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

Relationship between Independent Variable 2 and Dependent Variable: Sales Promotion and Ecommerce

Many sectors take great interest in E-commerce due to the fact that it is likely to bring a fundamental change in the business process management in the years to come. Plus the delivery services are also different from that of traditional ways (Alafeef, 2014). At present, companies should and have to adopt new methods to entertain their customers, increase sales and make a difference in the market through their performance (Alafeef, 2014). Because of the impact it has made, it validates the prosperity of E-commerce for the future. Now, both big and small initiatives start their venture by entering into the online marketplace while they are already aware of the competition with some leading brands. Keeping in regard the consumer's preferred interest these days that is to go to a store and their time commuting to and from the store (Prihantoro, 2018; Wiranata, & Hananto, 2020). Most of the time, consumers like it very much when they get to know about the online presence of any business. Sales promotion so far has been one of the effective mediums that helped various online platforms exist and offer services for their businesses (Zhu, Liu, & Chen, 2018). The prevalence of online shopping has also increased the irrational shopping behaviour such as impulse buying that makes up a large share of the revenue of E-retailer (Wiranata & Hananto, 2020).

On the contrary, retailers incorporate a mix of marketing and promotional strategies to keep going in the competition while maintaining a good pace because purchase decisions are acknowledged by the consumers through various advertisement promotional offers as per their behavioural shifts. Furthermore, In India, the consumers are growing at a good pace while the retailers find it extremely difficult to influence the customers about their purchasing decisions (Sharma & Avasthi, 2019). It was further studied and concluded that variations in the sales promotion tactics are required to attain new customers and maintain the existing ones while keeping youth the main target as they do not intend to switch brands or shops they usually purchase from (Sharma & Avasthi, 2019). More to this, it was further asserted that promotion is vital for success. It is necessary for any retail organisation if they want to compete greatly with their competitors. That is why a more customised and thoughtful approach is what we need alongside the advanced technology.

While the extant literature based on sales promotion has covered a variety of areas. Some focus on the performance, some on the promotion and its types while the others focus on the benefits (Zhu, Liu, & Chen, 2018). But all this while, a fact kept constant. It implied that different types of promotions affect the consumers' differently based on their purchase decisions and brand equity (Zhu, Liu, & Chen, 2018). Some of the early research on sales promotions emphasised on the effects of sales promotions; how it impacts the sales and profits and how the promotional effect impacts the purchasing behaviour of consumers during the promotional period (Mendez, Bendixen, Abratt, Yurova, & O'Leary, 2015). A survey was conducted while the result indicated that the quality of website did not affect impulse buying while the factors that affect impulse buying positively were found to be sales promotion and fashion consciousness (Wiranata & Hananto, 2020). It was suggested that not all promotional campaigns work in the same manner. They may

turn out differently but regarding the long term influence on reference price and the price observed at the moment of purchase is a fundamental aspect to look upon, that will never change (Diamond & Campbell, 1989).

H2: Sales promotion influences the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

Relationship between Independent Variable 3 and Dependent Variable: Online Buying Behaviour and Ecommerce

Online buying behaviour is a complex phenomenon that many researchers have researched upon in the past decade (Nazir, Tayyab, Rashid, Javed, & Sajid, 2012). Purchasing decisions made by the consumers are quite hard to analyse because it is almost impossible to predict consumer's psychology while making decisions and purchases. Because of this reason, this area has been the subject of research to find out about various factors. The understanding of complex phenomena of consumer behaviour can be acquired if the factors affecting purchasing decisions are neglected or not looked upon. For example, the consumers' fears while making online purchases are particularly regarded as influential factors in direct purchase decisions. It was also studied that internet shoppers were more impulsive than non-internet shoppers, making the evidence more obvious that impulse buying behaviour is more adamant in E-commerce settings (Liu, 2013). According to Rook (1987), "Impulse buying occurs when a consumer experiences a sudden, often powerful and persistent urge to buy something immediately" (Wiranata & Hananto, 2020). It was suggested that online shopping reflected rational and irrational behaviour, and in particular, irrational behaviour is made up of a large part for E-retailer revenue (Lo, 2016). This makes the implementation of impulse buying behaviour an interesting strategy for E-retailers (Wiranata & Hananto, 2020). Online impulse buying is an integral aspect of E-commerce, as the competition is rising between many potent E-commerce companies. The basic need of the time is to work harder, often through implementing manipulative marketing tactics and techniques to attract potential customers for their platforms (Wiranata & Hananto, 2020). It was further concluded that impulse buying on online platforms was the end product of consumer's inability to control their instincts in making choices while making a purchase (Lo, 2016; Wiranata & Hananto, 2020). Furthermore, studies concluded that impulse buying helps the retailers in attaining sales. So, impulse buying works as a sales driver for the retailers. Indonesia's E-commerce is a real time example that has been rapidly growing over the years. In Indonesia, around more than 90% of the people use the internet to buy goods and services (Badgaiyan & Verma, 2015; Kemp & Moey, 2019). However, there are also some other factors that may be the reason behind customer's online buying behaviour such as financial risk that is always a top concern for the buyers. Secondly, the product risk; because in traditional shopping buyers are able to have a look at the product in person that makes them sure about the quality of product rather than online stores, though they provide accurate descriptions of products and buyers are also able to zoom in on the product pictures but still, some of the buyers are not sure about the product quality. But other than this, one aspect that subsidizes them all is the convenience they get in online shopping. As per the results of the studies, people now not only use the internet to purchase products but also to compare other characteristics such as product price, product features. More than that, they also go through the reviews to acknowledge their customer service facilities that they may receive if they make a purchase from that particular store, online.

Concluding from all of the studies, that the process of impulse buying happens then and there without having a second giving it a second thought. Consumers do it with a positive mindset to get the products and services of their choice. In this process, they do not often consider the product cost seriously or the consequences the purchase may bring (Leong, 2018; Wiranata & Hananto, 2020).

H3: Online buying behavior influences the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

Relationship between Independent Variable 4 and Dependent Variable: Shopping Orientation and Ecommerce

From the consumer's point of view, online shopping provides the buyers a great margin that allows them to search and compare different product prices and service credibility, anywhere in all over the world. The interactive nature of the Internet offers opportunities for consumers to use the web shopping facilities effectively by improving the availability of product information, enabling direct multi attributes comparison, and reducing prospective buyers' information search costs (Alba, 1997; Ling, Chai, & Piew, 2010). From a

company's point of view, the use of the internet has risen in the consumers as their approach is also evolving with time. So, companies can take this as an opportunity to understand the shopping approach of their potential target customers. If they keep their research strong, they can attract a good number of potential customers (Ling, Chai, & Piew, 2010).

Therefore, it is important to understand the background of the perceptions of customer's orientations or motives, where they come from and how they come from. For this, not only the behavioural constructs but the psychological constructs are equally important and interconnected (Hanna & Wozniak, 2001; Morschett, Swoboda, & Klien, 2005). Although it is often considered that perceived shopping orientations and alternatives are independent, there is a debate that has an argument that though shopping orientations influence the perception but also it influences the attitude (Morschett, Swoboda, & Klien, 2005). More to this, in research, it is a common practice to classify the consumers through their shopping behavioral. Researchers identify the shoppers as "have to" shoppers, "moderate" shoppers, "experiential" shoppers, "product focused" shoppers, "service" shoppers, and "practical" shoppers, based on the features, shoppers put emphasis upon (Jarratt, 1996).

Once an individual's demographic and psychographic differences were measured, that had the potential to influence their shopping orientations. The results identified that women and men differ in keeping their approaches. They take convenience differently plus, they also take the concept of fashion conscious shopping orientation quite differently, but they do not differ in impulsive buying and in the consideration for the product quality, brand they are purchasing and product price orientation (Workman & Cho, 2012). Another study took place where the results reflected upon the understanding of young male consumers in online clothing shopping. The results identified that they are also convenience oriented, have an instinct for impulsive searching for discounts and besides this, the brand names and product price and quality matters no matter what (Workman & Cho, 2012).

Though there is an indication that shopping is considered as a task that should be completed as soon as possible. But the other shopping orientation is overshadowed by the fact that some of the people also take it as an enjoyment (Sinha, 2003). On the other hand, some of the research also implies that shopping orientations also directly influence the perceived brand image or image of a certain product (Morschett, Swoboda, & Klien, 2005). This indicates the relationship between shopping orientations and perception of attributes (Lumpkin, 1985; Mason, 1983; Osman 1993; Morschett, Swoboda, & Klien, 2005). On the other hand, several studies were held and the results identified that there seems to exist also a type of shoppers who are more price and convenience oriented while there also exist apathetic shoppers. They do not have much involvement in different shopping dimensions (Osman, 1993; Westbrook & Black, 1985).

H4: Shopping orientation influences the consumer buying behaviour in Ecommerce.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Methodology

Questionnaire Measurement of constructs

There were two parts of the survey questionnaire. Section one included demographic questions, while section two contained questions about four constructs derived from prior research. Product variety is evaluated from (Bakos,2001). where as Nidhi Sharma, Siddharth Das (2017) is modified to assess shopping orientation. E-commerce is evaluated by Safia Anjum and Junwu Chai (2020). Online buying behaviour is adopted from Teena bagga and Manas bhatt (2013).

Results

Results as per the age and gender

- Here, among 181 respondents, 7.7% from less than 21, 76.8% are the people having age ranging from 21 - 30, 9.4% from 31 - 40, 3.2% from 41 - 50 and 2.9% from 51 & above, respectively.
- And among 179 respondents, 69.3% are female while the other 30.7% are male.

Results as per the qualification and income of the family

- Here, among 178 respondents, 20.2% are upto intermediate, 60.1% are graduated, 15.2% have done masters, 4% have completed their MS/MPhil and 0.5% are doctorate, respectively.
- Here among 180 respondents, 0.2% have the income of upto 20,000, 8.9% have 21,000 - 30,000, 16.1% have 31,000 - 40,000 and 72.8% have the income of 41,000 & above, respectively.

Results as per the profession and flow of online shopping in the last month

- Here, among 180 respondents, 8.9% are in the profession of marketing, 6.7% are teachers, 67.8% are students, 4.5% are in engineering, 3% in banking, 1.5% are doctor, 1.9% in business, 1.9% in administration, 1.9% in income tax and 1.9% in freelance writing, respectively.
- Here, among 180 responses, 5% of the people did not shop online last month, while 41.1% did 1 - 5 times, 35% did 6 - 10 times and 18.9% did more than 11 times, respectively.

Demographics

Table 1

Age	Percentage (%)
Less than 21	7.7%
21 - 30	76.8%
31 - 40	9.4%
41 - 50	3.2%
51 & above	2.9%

*N=181 responses

Table 2

Gender	Percentage (%)
Male	30.7%
Female	69.3%

*N=179 responses

Table 3

Qualification	Percentage (%)
Upto Intermediate	20.2%

Graduated	60.1%
Masters	15.2%
MS/MPhil	4%
Doctorate	0.5%

*N=178 responses

Table 4

Income of the family	Percentage (%)
Upto 20, 000	0.2%
21, 000 - 30, 000	8.9%
31, 000 - 40, 000	16.1%
41, 000 & above	72.8%

*N=180 responses

Table 5

Profession	Percentage (%)
Marketing	8.9%
Banking	3%
Engineering	4.5%
Doctor	1.5%
Teacher	6.7%
Student	67.8%
Business	1.9%
Administration	1.9%
Income Tax	1.9%
Freelance Writer	1.9%

*N=180 responses

Table 6

How many times did they shop online?	Percentage (%)
0	5%
1 - 5	41.1%
6 - 10	35%
11 & above	18.9%

*N=180 responses

Table 7

Online shopping offers new experiences	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	40	22.1%
Agree	50	27.6%
Neutral	40	22.1%
Disagree	23	12.7%
Strongly Disagree	28	15.5%

*N=181 responses

Table 8

Ease of comparing the offerings of different vendors	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	38	21.1%
Agree	50	27.8%
Neutral	37	20.6%
Disagree	26	14.4%
Strongly Disagree	29	16.1%

*N=180 responses

Table 9

Refinement of taste in choosing goods	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	22	12.2%
Agree	58	32.2%
Neutral	46	25.6%
Disagree	29	16.1%
Strongly Disagree	25	13.9%

*N=180 responses

Table 10

Wide variety of goods and services	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	28	15.5%
Agree	56	30.9%
Neutral	40	22.1%
Disagree	13	7.2%
Strongly Disagree	44	24.3%

*N=181 responses

Table 11

Uncertainty when buying online	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	15	8.3%
Agree	30	16.7%
Neutral	58	32.2%
Disagree	44	24.4%
Strongly Disagree	33	18.3%

*N=180 responses

Table 12

Feel a sense of adventure	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	28	15.5%
Agree	55	30.4%
Neutral	41	22.7%
Disagree	32	17.7%
Strongly Disagree	25	13.8%

*N=181 reponses

Table 13

Inability to shop from far off locations	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	40	22.2%
Agree	51	28.3%
Neutral	38	21.1%
Disagree	24	13.3%
Strongly Disagree	27	15%

*N=180 responses

Table 14

Time spent on shopping is enjoyable	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	29	16.1%
Agree	50	27.8%
Neutral	42	23.3%
Disagree	30	16.7%
Strongly Disagree	29	16.1%

*N=180 responses

Table 15

Preference of online buying because it is easier	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	27	14.9%
Agree	45	24.9%
Neutral	57	31.5%
Disagree	26	14.4%
Strongly Disagree	26	14.4%

*N=181 responses

Table 16

Find trustworthy websites based on the ratings	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	26	14.4%
Agree	48	26.5%
Neutral	45	24.9%
Disagree	30	16.6%
Strongly Disagree	32	17.7%

*N=181 responses

Table 17

Buy things whenever I want	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	36	20%
Agree	43	23.9%
Neutral	40	22.2%
Disagree	30	16.7%
Strongly Disagree	31	17.2%

*N=180 responses

Table 18

Feel risk in paying through E-payment	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	24	13.4%
Agree	38	21.2%
Neutral	41	22.9%
Disagree	34	19%
Strongly Disagree	42	23.5%

*N=179 responses

Table 19

Identification of marketing factors on consumer behaviour	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	15	8.3%
Agree	52	28.7%
Neutral	56	30.9%
Disagree	23	12.7%
Strongly Disagree	35	19.3%

*N=181 responses

Table 20

Cost reducing and time saving	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	30	16.7%
Agree	55	30.6%
Neutral	39	21.7%
Disagree	31	17.2%
Strongly Disagree	25	13.9%

*N=180 responses

Table 21

Feeling of trustability in online buying in Pakistan	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	17	9.4%
Agree	47	26.1%
Neutral	53	29.4%
Disagree	33	18.3%
Strongly Disagree	30	16.7%

*N=180 responses

Table 22

Consistency of online purchasing behaviour and emotional stability	No. of persons	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	19	10.5%
Agree	44	24.3%
Neutral	61	33.7%
Disagree	27	14.9%
Strongly Disagree	30	16.6%

*N=181 responses

Discussion

It has been seen in the results that regardless of untrustworthiness, the new trend of online shopping has invoked its influence on the people. Many people have started preferring online shopping over the traditional one. One of the reasons found in the survey was that the customers get plenty of options to choose from. And they can do it just within a click of a mouse. That makes things a lot easier and more convenient. This is because, in traditional shopping, sometimes customers purchase things at high prices but in online shopping, there is no negotiation. The price is fixed and oftentimes, it is comparatively low. Another reason for choosing online shopping over traditional one is, the customers get a wide variety of products with a variation price range; that makes it easy enough for them to decide and choose from. As different people have different tastes, they get a wide variety of things of their own taste when they shop online. Though, the quality is not guaranteed when it comes to online shopping but the feasibility of purchasing from far off locations grants the chance of risk. As per the results of the survey, people find it really easy to purchase things online. They even enjoy their time in doing so. The results also reflect on the fact that people also value the available ratings of the products and services. Through this approach, they select and buy things from tons of options. Furthermore, customers consider this an opportunity to buy things whenever they want. Not only this, but this method of shopping is also more convenient, quick, time saving and cost saving. With the passage of time, this trend of shopping has become a common thing now and customers are partially consistent about their buying behaviour based on their emotional stability.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Supported/Non Supported
H1	Supported
H2	Supported
H3	Supported
H4	Supported
H5	Non Supported
H6	Supported

Conclusion

In Pakistan, online shopping has emerged with a great pace which influenced the lives of ordinary citizens (Rahman, Islam, Esha, Sultana, & Chakravorty, 2018). To validate this statement, online shopping is getting trendier in Pakistan as well as in the rest of the world but the velocity of online shopping in Pakistan is slower as compared to the entire world. According to a survey, online shopping is getting popular among the young generation such as students and professionals where students usually prefer to buy goods from their original source and they mostly prefer online shopping. While when a consumer makes purchases online to buy something (Nazir, Tayyab, Sajid, Rashid , & Javed, 2012), they are concerned about some of the factors such as price, security, convenience, time, after sale service and discounted deals (Nazir, Tayyab, Sajid, Rashid , & Javed, 2012) and not to mention the credibility of the product. A survey revealed that consumers shop online to save time, and for available varieties of products and services while both males and females have the same type of behaviour towards liking and disliking factors; they like home delivery facilities and dislike most the inability to touch and feel the product (Rahman, Islam, Esha, Sultana , & Chakravorty, 2018). Consumers prefer to shop online because the prices are often lower at online shops as compared to the physical stores as they have a great margin to negotiate. Buying online can be of great benefit in terms of convenience, saving time and money while one of the prime obstacles (Nazir, Tayyab, Sajid, Rashid , & Javed, 2012) that the consumers face in online shopping is when the system asks for the complete details of the customers including the bank details etc. Due to which, a customer gets anxious that their personal details may get disclosed (Nazir, Tayyab, Sajid, Rashid , & Javed, 2012) or violated, which makes trust and confidence also an important factor (Nazir, Tayyab, Sajid, Rashid , & Javed, 2012).

Limitations and Recommendations

Though this research has covered various aspects regarding the area of consumer buying behaviour in E-Commerce, still there are some that have not been discussed in this study. However, the examination of the independent variables in the literature review may provide clues about the facts and figures of things that are evolving with time. Since, the time span of this research was quite short. Therefore, there are various aspects and areas that are not covered in this study. More to this, the development of such a measure was beyond the scope of this thesis. So, we tried to bring light on the impact of various independent variables with respect to the consumer buying behaviour in E-commerce.

Future Dimensions

In this study, some unanswered questions have been exposed. For this, the researcher would recommend broadening the area of research in future, to have a better understanding of interlinked concepts, also promoting this business sector in the future to create stable E-commerce platforms.

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